

CURRENT ISSUES IN ORGANIZING NURSING CARE FOR ESSENTIAL ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION IN ADOLESCENTS IN PRIMARY HEALTH CARE

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Abstract. *This article describes a preventive examination and its results conducted in the 46th secondary school of the Kibray district of the Tashkent region. The purpose of the study was: based on a comprehensive assessment of the activities of nursing staff, to assess the health status and risk factors for the development of disease in adolescents. Essential arterial hypertension was identified in 21.5% of adolescents. The results of the study showed that the most significant provoking factors were: a sedentary lifestyle, excess weight, fatigue during extracurricular activities, sleeping less than 6 hours a day, consuming a lot of salt and smoking. During nursing care, patients were prescribed additional methods, such as: a salt-free diet, reducing calorie intake, taking medications regularly, and engaging in active sports.*

Keywords: *essential arterial hypertension, primary health care, organization of nursing care, adolescents, risk factors.*

Relevance of the Problem. Essential arterial hypertension (EAH) is a disease whose primary, and sometimes the only, clinical symptom is an elevated blood pressure level [8, pp. 202-204]. Factors playing a significant role in the onset and development of hypertension in young individuals include age, gender, smoking, stress, hereditary predisposition, low physical activity, excessive body weight, and disorders of carbohydrate, lipid, and purine metabolism. According to research conducted in our country and elsewhere, hypertension is observed in 2.4–18% of children, depending on age [6, pp. 74-78]. In children and adolescents, hypertension occurs much less frequently than in adults [8, pp. 202-204]. Before the age of 10, essential hypertension is observed in 10% of children, while symptomatic hypertension accounts for 90% of cases. With age, the incidence of essential hypertension increases, reaching 35% in adolescents.

Recently, there has been a growing trend in hypertension cases among children, primarily due to the increasing prevalence of obesity among children and adolescents [8, pp. 202-204]. In children and adolescents with hypertension, moderate hypertension is most commonly observed, characterized by a slight increase in blood pressure (BP). Clinical data indicate an increased reactivity of heart rate (HR) and BP in response to stress or other stimuli [6, pp. 74-78]. Epidemiological studies have established that hypertension occurs in up to 30% of overweight children. Moreover, an increase in body mass index (BMI) is associated with a higher incidence of hypertension [8, pp. 202-204].

Children and adolescents with high BP are more likely than those with normal BP to be diagnosed with cardiovascular risk factors such as hyperinsulinemia, abdominal obesity, elevated triglyceride (TG) levels, and reduced high-density lipoprotein (HDL) levels [3, pp. 152-156]. The future course of hypertension in children and adolescents remains a matter of concern. Long-term observations show that hypertension progresses in 25% of adolescents and remains persistently

high in 33–42% of cases [8, pp. 202-204]. A strong correlation has been identified between BP levels in childhood and adolescence and BP levels in adulthood [3, pp. 152-156]. Between the ages of 7 and 17, the incidence of hypertension rises from 3.9% to 14.3%, and by the age of 30, it increases to 18.4% [6, pp. 74-78]. If systolic blood pressure (SBP) exceeds the 90th percentile in childhood, the likelihood of elevated SBP persisting into adulthood is 24% [4, pp. 152-156].

Several studies have assessed the relationship between gender and the frequency of hypertension (HTN) development. According to the EPOCH study (2004), it was found that among individuals aged 20-29, women suffered from HTN in 1.6% of cases, whereas men had a prevalence of 4.8%, indicating a higher incidence of HTN in young men [4, pp. 152-156]. A weak correlation between gender and systolic blood pressure (SBP) as well as diastolic blood pressure (DBP) was observed. The correlation coefficient for SBP was 0.39 in men compared to 0.38 in women, while for DBP, it was 0.29 versus 0.26, respectively [8, pp. 202-204]. Other studies, however, did not reveal significant differences in blood pressure levels between men and women with HTN [4, pp. 152-156]. Further research is necessary to clarify the differences in the relationship between gender and blood pressure levels in children and adults.

Several studies have demonstrated the impact of heredity on the development of HTN. The prevalence of HTN is significantly higher in families where members suffer from HTN compared to families of healthy individuals [3, pp. 152-156]. Genetic predisposition accounts for 20-40% of cases of HTN. If one parent has HTN, the risk of developing hypertension in children is 27%, whereas if both parents are affected, the risk increases to 50%. Additionally, the frequency of HTN development in children also depends on gender. If one parent has HTN, the condition is observed in girls 2.4 times more often than in the control group, while in boys, it occurs 1.9 times more often. If both parents have HTN, the likelihood increases 6.2 times in girls and 3.9 times in boys compared to the control group [3, pp. 152-156].

It is widely known that smoking increases the risk of cardiovascular diseases (CVD). In recent years, there has been a trend toward a younger age at which regular smoking begins. Among individuals aged 15-24, up to 23% smoke regularly, while in the 25-34 age group, this figure reaches 30% [3, pp. 152-156]. Recent data from Canadian researchers indicate that approximately 25% of girls and up to 19% of young men aged 15-17 smoke, with the percentage equalizing to 31% by the age of 19. Furthermore, differences in the number of cigarettes smoked per day have been observed—young men smoke 17% more than young women and tend to increase their cigarette consumption more rapidly [3, pp. 152-156].

It has been proven that low physical activity is one of the risk factors for developing HTN. Prospective studies indicate that individuals with a sedentary and inactive lifestyle have a 20-50% higher risk of developing HTN compared to those who lead an active lifestyle [6, pp. 74-78].

Several studies on both adults and young individuals have identified a strong correlation between blood pressure levels and body mass index (BMI) [4, pp. 152-156]. Among patients with HTN, 73% have excessive body weight. Individuals with excess body weight develop HTN approximately eight years earlier, and mortality rates among them are 12 times higher than in the general population [6, pp. 74-78]. Similar findings have been obtained from studies on young individuals. If one parent has obesity, the child's risk of developing excess body weight ranges from 30-60%; if both parents are obese, the probability rises to 80%. Therefore, the influence of heredity must be considered in young individuals [2, pp. 100–104].

According to the Community Hypertension Clinic Study, the likelihood of hypertension (HTN) in individuals with obesity was twice as high as in those with normal body weight. The Framingham Study identified an association between an increase in systolic blood pressure (SBP) by 4 mmHg with a weight gain of 4.5 kg [3, pp. 152-156]. The rising prevalence of obesity among children is of particular concern. Worldwide, the number of obese children has been doubling every three decades. Over the past 20 years, obesity prevalence among children aged 6 to 11 years has doubled (from 7% to 13%), while among adolescents aged 12 to 19 years, it has nearly tripled (from 5% to 14%). Currently, up to 25% of adolescents are overweight, and 15% suffer from obesity [6, pp. 74-78]. A significant increase in obesity rates among the 35-year-old population was projected by 2020 [4, pp. 152-156].

Numerous studies conducted over the years have firmly established a link between childhood body mass index (BMI) and the development of HTN in adulthood [2,7,8,9]. Insulin resistance is currently considered a pre-diabetic condition and is frequently observed in overweight children [10,11,12]. A shift in the lipid spectrum toward an atherogenic profile is characteristic of children with metabolic syndrome (MS) combined with HTN, increasing the likelihood of developing ischemic heart disease and diabetes mellitus (DM) [2, pp. 100–104]. Data on the relationship between blood pressure (BP) and lipid spectrum disorders remain contradictory; however, a correlation has been identified between elevated total cholesterol (TC) levels in blood serum and BP levels [2, pp. 100–104].

Materials and Methods. This study describes a preventive medical examination and its results, conducted at School No. 46 in the Kibray district of Tashkent region. The aim of the study was to assess the health status and risk factors for disease development among adolescents based on a comprehensive evaluation of nursing staff performance. Additionally, a prospective analysis of 201 adolescent questionnaires with essential arterial hypertension (EAH) was conducted. The study also included an analysis of the quality of medical care provided to adolescents with EAH, involving 30 nurses working at the central multidisciplinary polyclinic of the Kibray district.

To achieve the research objectives and obtain reliable and objective results, a set of modern social-hygienic and general scientific research methods were used, including analytical, sociological (survey), statistical, and instrumental methods.

Study Subjects. 201 adolescents from School No. 46 in the Kibray district of Tashkent region. Nurses from the central multidisciplinary polyclinic of the Kibray district providing primary medical and sanitary care (PMSC) to the population with HTN.

Research Subject

- Organization of nursing care for adolescents with essential arterial hypertension (EAH) in primary healthcare settings.
- Social predictors of quality of life (QoL) prognosis and the process of organizing primary medical and sanitary care (PMSC) for adolescents suffering from EAH.

Group I (Control Group) – 171 practically healthy adolescents who visited the clinic due to a single episode of elevated blood pressure but were not registered for regular medical follow-up.

Group II (Main Group) – 30 adolescents with EAH who were under regular medical supervision and received standard nursing care from specially trained nurses. This care was optimized with additional measures, including the implementation of modern clinical protocols, remote monitoring, and the establishment of a "Hypertension Health School."

- Registration with the local primary healthcare clinic.
- Voluntary informed consent.
- Age range: 10–19 years.
- Refusal to participate in the study.
- Presence of severe comorbid conditions.

Table 2.1.1.

Steps of Research

Stage of research	Observation Unit	Source of information	Number of patients	Research method
Stage I (2019) – Organizational and Analytical Definition of the research object, scope, observation unit; selection and description of research methods and research procedures. Retrospective analysis of morbidity and frequency of Essential Arterial Hypertension (EAH) in the <u>Kibray</u> district of Tashkent region for the years 2015–2019.	- Medical Documentation and Study Groups. Medical records of patients with hypertension (HTN) who underwent scheduled dispensary examinations from 2015 to 2019.	Report on the number of diseases registered among patients residing in the healthcare institution's service area -"Statistical Card for Recording Final Diagnoses," Form No. 025-2/u -"Outpatient Patient Registration Journal," Form No. 074/u -"Outpatient Medical Record," Form No. 025 -"Control Card for Dispensary Observation," Form No. 030/u	1,082 patients with cardiovascular diseases (CVD).	Analytical. statistical. sociological.
Stage II (2020–2021) – Prospective Analysis. Prospective analysis of patients with arterial hypertension (AH) registered for dispensary observation. Collection of medical and social information. Survey (adherence, quality of life, awareness, patient satisfaction).	- Patients with HTN registered for dispensary observation at the Central Multidisciplinary Polyclinic of <u>Kibray</u> District. - Nurses from the Central Multidisciplinary Polyclinic of <u>Kibray</u> District providing primary medical and sanitary care (PMSC) to the adult population with HTN.	-"Outpatient Medical Record," Form No. 025 -"Control Card for Dispensary Observation," Form No. 030/u (family history, smoking status, lipid profile, glucose level, waist circumference, risk factor analysis, overall cardiovascular risk assessment using the SCORE2 scale) -Assessment of patients' quality of life (QoL) using the SF-36 questionnaire -Survey based on tailored questionnaires for patients and nurses	120 patients, 20 nurses.	Analytical. statistical. sociological.
Stage III (2021–2022) – Clinical and Instrumental Examination. Clinical and instrumental examination and survey of patients with high and very high cardiovascular risk (adherence, quality of life, anxiety).	Main group (80 people) – Application of a new methodological approach to cardiovascular disease (CVD) prevention during age-specific dispensary examinations. Comparison group (40 people) – Standard dispensary observation procedures.	- Clinical and instrumental examination (blood pressure measurement, ECG, anthropometry, assessment of family history, harmful habits, blood glucose level, lipid metabolism, risk factor analysis, quality of life assessment, overall cardiovascular risk). -Survey based on tailored questionnaires for patients and nurses before the implementation of the optimized nursing care program for patients with hypertension.	120 patients, 30 nurses.	Analytical, statistical, sociological, clinical, biochemical, instrumental.
Stage IV (2022–2023) – Effectiveness Evaluation Assessment of effectiveness. Development and implementation of proposals for improvement.	Study Groups and Nursing Involvement. Main group (80 people) – Implementation of a new methodological approach to cardiovascular disease (CVD) prevention during age-specific dispensary examinations. Comparison group (40 people) – Standard dispensary observation procedures. Nurses from the Central Multidisciplinary Polyclinic of <u>Kibray</u> District providing primary medical and sanitary care (PMSC) to the adult population with hypertension (HTN).	-Collection of information from the electronic health diary "Health Diary" of a patient with hypertension. -Determination of adherence indicators to prevention measures and organization of medical and preventive care in dynamics with an assessment of effectiveness. -Survey based on tailored questionnaires for patients and nurses after the implementation of the optimized nursing care program for patients with hypertension.	120 patients, 30 nurses.	Analytical, statistical, sociological, clinical, biochemical, instrumental.

Research Implementation. The research program was conducted in several stages in accordance with the study's objectives and goals. The study spanned two years (2020–2021) and included four phases:

1. Preparatory (organizational) phase
2. Collection of medical and social data
3. Implementation of new approaches
4. Analysis of obtained data and evaluation of effectiveness

The stages and study design are presented in Table 2.1.1.

Study Participants and Procedures. In accordance with the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 201 adolescents with EAH were initially selected for preventive screening under the age-specific medical examination program and the implementation of an optimized nursing care program.

At the initial clinic visit, all participants underwent:

- Primary risk assessment
- Questionnaire survey (assessing quality of life levels, adherence to preventive measures, and anxiety levels)
- Standard medical check-up, including: Anthropometric measurements, blood pressure monitoring (tonometry), electrocardiography (ECG), clinical examination

The patient survey included a questionnaire assessing risk factors, followed by a physician-led medical examination in the consultation office.

Research Results. Research results. The conducted study revealed that the number of boys in the study group was higher than that of girls, accounting for 60.83% boys and 39.17% girls. Age group distribution showed that:

- Early adolescents (under 14 years) – 12.5%
- Ages 14–15 – 25.83%
- Ages 16–17 – 20%
- Ages 18–19 – 2.5%

The diagnosis of essential arterial hypertension (EAH) was confirmed in 72.5% of the patients. All patients belonged to Health Groups 1 and 2.

The most significant risk factors identified included:

- Sedentary lifestyle – 71.5%
- Excess body weight – 43.3%
- Fatigue during school activities – 23.33%
- Sleep duration less than 6 hours per day – 38.33%
- High salt intake – 20.0%
- Smoking – 2.67%

The primary complaints among adolescents were:

- Headaches
- Occasional darkening before the eyes
- Rapid fatigue

As part of nursing care, additional methods were prescribed, including:

- Salt-free diet
- Reduced calorie intake

Evaluation of health improvement activities showed that most adolescents actively followed the prescribed medical recommendations and expressed confidence in the effectiveness of the treatment.

Conclusions. The study found that 72.5% of adolescents were diagnosed with EAH. The most significant risk factors included sedentary lifestyle, excess body weight, fatigue, insufficient sleep (less than 6 hours), high salt intake, and smoking. Nursing care interventions included a salt-free diet, reduced calorie intake, and regular medication use. All at-risk patients were advised to eliminate these provoking factors to prevent the progression of hypertension.

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